

On the Relevance of Static Cells for Fast Scale-Up of New Redox Flow Battery Chemistries

Lara Lubian^[a,b], Ruben Rubio-Presa^[a], Roberto Sanz,^[b] Virginia Ruiz*^[a,b], Edgar Ventosa*^[a,b]

^a International Research Center in Critical Raw Materials-ICCRAM, Universidad de Burgos, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, E-09001, Burgos, Spain.

^b Departamento de Química, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Burgos, Pza. Misael Bañuelos s/n, E-09001-Burgos, Spain.

E-mail: vrfernandez@ubu.es and eventosa@ubu.es

Abstract

The search for organic electroactive molecules suitable in Aqueous Organic Flow Batteries requires great efforts not only from an electrochemical perspective (weeks of testing), but also from an organic synthesis viewpoint. This work focuses on the relevance of static cells for accelerating the search and helping understand degradation mechanisms. After disclosing an easy-to-make and reliable static cell, its validation is carried out using a few milligrams of model materials, i.e. ferrocyanide-based electrolyte. A simple but effective approach is proposed to investigate active species in the absence of air, which is based on the use of a cheap lunch box (Ar-box) in contrast to the expensive Ar-filled glovebox. The relevance of the proposed strategy is demonstrated by investigating two case studies. The 2,6-dihydroxantraquinone/ $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in alkaline is studied with and without Ar-box. The air leakage in our static cell in the Ar-box is neglectable, so an Ar-filled glovebox is not needed. Interestingly, the use of Ar-box leads to higher capacity fading (1.3 vs 2.5% day⁻¹) since a very small leakage of air prevents the formation of dimers. In neutral pH, the total absence of air using 1,1-bis[3-sulfonatopropyl]-4,4-bipyridinium/ $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ static cell in the Ar-box leads to an increase in capacity fading (0.2% day⁻¹) compared to reported values using Ar-filled glovebox.

Keywords: Aqueous organic redox flow battery, static battery, scaling AORFB technology.

1. Introduction

Current demand for energy in society requires wide deployment of renewable energy sources to achieve the goal of zero emissions, decarbonization and the transition to a more sustainable energy production.^[1] However, the inherent unpredictability and intermittency of renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind power, demands efficient and cost-effective energy storage systems (ESSs) to match energy production and demand.^[2,3] Redox flow batteries (RFB) are particularly suitable for large-scale stationary energy storage, offering competitive advantages over conventional batteries such as cost-effectiveness, long cycle life and independent scalability of energy and power.^[3] Currently, the All-Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (AVRFB) represents the state-of-art in RFB technology, but it faces important challenges, including the use of a critical raw material and highly corrosive strongly acidic solutions.^[3] This has triggered interest in more sustainable and safer alternatives, such as aqueous organic redox flow batteries (AORFB), where inorganic redox species are replaced by more sustainable and abundant organic redox-active compounds.^[3] Additionally, it has been demonstrated that the cost of the organic redox-active materials can be less than USD 35 per kWh, highlighting their cost competitiveness.^[4] Driven by these economic, social and safety considerations, several types of redox-active compounds have been explored for both compartments of the AORFB^[5-7]. Most molecule families investigated for the anolyte include quinones^[8-10], viologens^[11-14] and aza-aromatic compounds.^[15] For the AORFB catholyte, the most commonly used redox pair is low cost ferrocyanide/ferricyanide $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN}_6)]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN}_6)]^{3-}$ ^[16], although other redox active species including metallocenes^[17] and heterocyclic nitroxide radical derivatives^[6] have also been explored. Despite remarkable recent progress in development of high-performing redox molecules, these active materials often face challenges such as limited chemical/electrochemical stability and low water solubility.^[18] These issues make it difficult to achieve the long lifetime and high energy density required for practical applications. Hence, considerable efforts are expected to be devoted in the near future to the development of new organic redox molecules by molecular engineering with improved physicochemical properties to mitigate energy storage capacity fading in AORFB^[2,19,20]. Degradation of active species due to molecular incompatibility or intrinsic decomposition^[2,3,19] is the main source of capacity fading in AORFB, with cell design-related aspects such as membrane degradation, electrolyte leakage or crossover also contributing.^[20] Additionally, a third source of capacity fading is faradaic imbalance between both sides of the RFB due to parasitic side reactions such as hydrogen and oxygen evolution or oxygen reduction.^[21] Identifying the contribution of each source using suitable

characterization techniques is crucial to develop strategies to prevent or minimize capacity fading.^[16,22,23] Thus, search for competitive electrolyte active molecules requires establishing experimental methodologies for fast-screening of different electrolyte compositions that can provide insights into possible degradation mechanisms. Common approaches applied for redox active molecules filtering/screening are schematically depicted in Figure 1.

As an initial step of the screening process at the funnel entry (Figure 1), computational modeling and simulation is a powerful tool to predict chemical and electrochemical properties of active species, accelerating the search for new redox compound families. Modeling allows high-throughput screening of numerous molecules, predicting target properties such as solubility, cyclability, multi-electron usability, stability and redox potential.^[22,23] Additionally, modeling and simulation provides understanding of reaction mechanisms and battery performance aimed at design optimization without the need of experimental work.^[24] As a next step in the screening process, the behavior of active species in terms of solubility and electrochemical properties, such as charge transfer kinetics, reversibility and stability, is assessed experimentally. This second filter involves synthesis of the novel active species at small scale (hundreds of milligrams) to evaluate their redox properties by standard electrochemical techniques such as cyclic voltammetry^[25–28], scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM)^[26] or rotating disk electrode measurements.^[27] Well-performing candidate molecules for AORFB are then moved to a next evaluation stage in a flow battery system^[25–28] to assess their suitability as electrolyte redox active species (Filter 3, Figure 1). This experimental evaluation in a flow system requires scaling up production of the novel molecule to gram quantities, which is more resource-consuming (materials, time, labour, cost) than the second filter step. In some cases, molecules with promising electrochemical properties exhibit poor cycling performance in flow system, as we will show in this manuscript. Hence, additional candidates are explored by re-starting the screening process from the first step, which implied significant loss of resources and time in the filter 3 step. To overcome the need of large amounts of active material of flow systems, we propose the use of low-volume static cells as an intermediate filter between the second and third ones. The proposed intermediate filter consists of applying an experimental methodology that requires active species at the milligram scale. So far surprisingly underused to explore active species,^[29,30] this manuscript highlights the power of static cells for fast assessment and scaling of new RFB chemistries. Material screening in low-volume static cells is a simple and cost-effective methodology to optimize resources accessible to any research laboratory.

Specifically, small volumes (2 mL) of solutions containing the active species are prepared and a portion of it is injected into a miniaturized static battery, sealed to prevent leakage, where flow is eliminated to simplify the system. A static battery cell was designed, 3D-printed and validated using potassium ferrocyanide. Additionally, an experimental set-up to prevent oxygen entry into the cell is reported, which allows evaluating active species without the need of a glove box, sometimes unavailable to some researchers. We will show how the static cell is suitable for evaluating cycling stability of new families of redox active molecules, offering a preliminary assessment without the need to scale up material synthesis to gram quantities. Moreover, it allows the study of different degradation mechanisms for molecules in basic and neutral media. We believe that this methodology can contribute to a faster large-scale deployment of AORFB by identifying high-performing active molecules while providing better understanding of degradation processes that limit their cycling stability.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the screening process of novel active species for scaling AORFB technology and the new methodology developed.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Design and validation of the developed methodology.

To illustrate the important role of static cells to bridge the gap between current material screening approach (Figure 1) and reduce material needs, fluorescein was initially selected for the proof of concept. It represents an example of a potential good candidate molecule to be scaled up for laboratory-scale AORFB tests (Filter 3) based on electrochemical characterization (Filter 2). Fluorescein exhibits redox activity and is used in ophthalmic medicine as a fluorescent marker. Hence, in principle, it has potential as a non-toxic potential redox active candidate for safe AORFB in the event of an electrolyte leak during battery operation. According to the standard screening process, after pre-selection fluorescein would be subject to electrochemical characterization (Filter 2), requiring a few milligrams sample. Specifically, in our case, cyclic voltammetry (CV) was used to evaluate the electrochemical properties of fluorescein (0.025 g were used). Figure 2A shows CV of fluorescein at different scan rates. Based on its apparent reversible electrochemistry and negative redox potential, it would be inferred that fluorescein holds promise as an active molecule for AORFB anolyte. Therefore, conventional performance assessment approaches would imply moving to the Filter 3 and conduct cycling stability tests in a flow battery system.^[25–28] However, as indicated above, implementing this Filter 3 is a big leap that involves larger-scale material procurement (at gram scale) and can be resource-consuming. To illustrate the importance of an intermediate filter step, the performance of fluorescein as AORFB anolyte was evaluated in a flow battery. A battery was assembled with fluorescein (1.3 g) in alkaline medium as anolyte and an oversized potassium ferrocyanide catholyte to avoid faradaic imbalance. Figure 2B shows the voltage profile for the first charge-discharge cycle of the fluorescein//K₄Fe(CN)₆ flow battery, revealing that fluorescein can only be charged but not discharged. Post-mortem NMR analysis of the anolyte confirms the degradation of fluorescein (Figure S1). A comprehensive understanding of the degradation pathways requires in-depth and in-situ analysis. At this stage, we can conclude that fluorescein undergoes a slow, irreversible reduction process, which appears to be kinetically hindered and thus not readily observable in cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements. This poor performance as active molecule for the anolyte is somehow unexpected in view of its promising electrochemical characterization. Ruling out fluorescein as AORFB anolyte material by means of flow battery tests demanded a significant amount of a material that eventually turned out to be unusable, with the consequent synthetic effort. Thus, this molecule is a clear example to highlight the need of applying assessment methodologies that rely on small-scale sample amounts.

Figure 2. Case study of fluorescein testing as a promising molecule for AORFB. (A) Cyclic voltammetry of 0.2 M fluorescein in 1.5 M KOH at different scan rates. (B) Voltage-capacity profile for the first charge-discharge cycle at $\pm 30 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ with voltage limits of +1.75 / +0.5 V. Catholyte: 45 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide in 1 M KOH with a pH of 14; anolyte: 10 mL of 0.2 M fluorescein in 1.4 M KOH with a pH of 14.

With the aim of minimizing material needs, a methodology for fast screening active species at the milligram scale has been developed and is proposed to be used as an intermediate filter between the second and third ones (Figure 1). In this methodology, a small volume (2 mL) of the active species solutions is injected into miniaturized static batteries/cells, which allow evaluating stability of active species without resorting to the gram scale. Eliminating the flow in this static cell configuration is advantageous as in many occasions flow in RFB causes problems such as electrolyte leaks, osmosis through the membrane or tube breaking due to friction with the pump, as illustrated in Figure S2. These issues could be circumvented by stopping the flow in a RFB to analyze the active species. However, this strategy is not a good option because large volume of electrolyte is still required and charged/discharged active species diffuse away from the reactor into the tubes (Figure S3), leading to wrong conclusions about their stability.

The configuration and components of the static cell developed to evaluate active species for RFB is shown schematically in Figure 3. Detailed plans and exact dimensions of the components of the 3D-printed static cell are given in Figure S4. Although this static cell was fabricated by 3D printing, it could be also manufactured using a milling machine. As its large flow cell counterparts, the miniaturized static cell essentially consists of a filter-pressed cell using expanded graphite (SGL Carbon), graphite felt (SGL Carbon) and Nafion 212 (Ion

Power) as current collector, electrode and ion selective membrane, respectively sandwiched between two printed pieces of resin. Additionally, two Viton® gaskets (2 mm thick), having a cavity carved with a scalpel to insert the graphite felts, were used to seal the cell. Felt electrodes were activated by thermal treatment at 400 °C for two days before assembling the cell, and Viton® gaskets were pierced with needles for electrolyte injection. These needles should be placed at the opposite ends of the cavity to facilitate filling of the cell (Figure 3B). All cell components, except the Nafion membrane, have holes at the corners for screws to keep all the pieces joined and the cell tightly sealed. A previously calibrated torque wrench was used to ensure applying a homogeneous pressure to all the screws. Once the cell is assembled, the electrolytes (previously purged with argon, if needed) are injected with the help of a syringe from bottom to top. The electrolyte should be injected slowly until it flows out of the top needles (Figure 3C). A total volume of 2 mL is injected (although the internal volume is less, approx. 0.38 mL) to ensure complete filling of the cavity. Photographs of the different components and the injection configuration are shown in Figure S5.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of the static cell experimental set up. (A) Components of the static cell. (B) Position of carbon felt and needles in the Viton® gasket. (C) Schematics illustrating injection of the active species solution.

An initial validation of the static cell to mimic flow cell characterization was done during galvanostatic cycling of a symmetric potassium ferrocyanide/ferricyanide redox cell. One compartment was oversized (Non-Limiting Compartment - NLC), with 2 mL of 0.6 M potassium ferricyanide, while the other compartment (Limiting Compartment - LC) had 2 mL of 0.1 M potassium ferrocyanide in 0.5 M of KCl. Thus, electrochemical data can be attributed to the LC (less total active species), which becomes the “working compartment”, while the NLC, with more total active species, acts as “counter-compartment”. Moreover, using a large excess of active species in the counter-compartment reduces capacity fading due to occurrence of parasitic reactions. For this validation test, 84 mg of the capacity-limiting species (potassium ferrocyanide) were used, which illustrates the small amount of active species needed to evaluate their cycling performance in this cell. Figure 4A shows the first charge and discharge profiles of this symmetric static cell, and Figure 4B plots the evolution of discharge capacity and coulombic efficiency with the cycles. As expected for the stable potassium ferrocyanide/ferricyanide redox pair, high coulombic efficiency (ca. 100%) and stable discharge capacity was obtained for at least 45 cycles with this cell. As it has been demonstrated that capacity fading can be associated with the utilization rate of the active species,^[31] the volume of electrolyte used upon cycling of these cells was evaluated by applying a constant potential at the end of the galvanostatic charging and discharging steps. In this cell, the utilization rate without the constant voltage step was > 99% (Table S1), implying that all the electrolyte is used during galvanostatic cycling at 5 mA cm⁻². Furthermore, it is worth noting the high reproducibility of the static cell, as shown by the comparable discharge capacity values (1.02 ± 0.05 mAh, R.S.D. = 5 %) obtained in 4 replicate galvanostatic cycling tests (Table S5) for fresh solutions of potassium ferrocyanide/ferricyanide injected in 4 different static cells assembled with the same Viton® gaskets and felt electrodes. It should be noted that voltage profiles for charge and discharge do not cross at 0.0 V, but they do at -0.1 V. This is due to the excess of active species in the NLC. Thus, the charge / discharge cut-off voltage limits are not symmetrical.

Figure 4. Validation of the static cell for galvanostatic cycling of a symmetric potassium ferrocyanide/ferricyanide redox cell at $\pm 5 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ with voltage limits of $-0.35 / +0.3 \text{ V}$. (A) Voltage-capacity profile for the first charge-discharge cycle. (B) Discharge capacity and Coulombic efficiency versus number of cycles. Catholyte: approx. 0.38 mL of 0.1 M potassium ferrocyanide in 0.5 M KCl with a pH of 7.40; anolyte: approx. 0.38 mL of 0.6 M potassium ferricyanide with a pH of 5.6.

After validation of the static cell with well-known ferrocyanide/ferricyanide model system, we proved its power as screening tool requiring small amount of the new candidate active materials. Thus, for the case study of fluorescein, only 0.19 g would have been used in this static cell (Figure S6) to draw the same conclusion as with the RFB system (Figure 2B), which is an order of magnitude less than the amount used in the flow configuration. The results show that the static cell methodology can be regarded as an intermediate step for faster and resource-efficient evaluation of promising molecules based on electrochemical tests prior to undertaking further synthetic efforts scaling up for flow cell tests. Moreover, the potential of static cells to study molecule degradation mechanisms will be discussed in next sections. It should be noted that the error in calculating theoretical capacity and energy density is directly proportional to the cell's volume for small volumes. Given the inherent challenges in accurately estimating theoretical capacity, this technique is designed as an intermediate screening tool to be used before full-scale flow battery evaluation. Therefore, static cells should not replace traditional flow battery testing, but rather complement it by providing a preliminary assessment of the potential stability of new active species.

2.2. Probing degradation mechanism of an alkaline DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ RFB with the static cell.

A quinone derivative was initially selected to illustrate the potential of the static cell to study stability of active molecules, due to the relevance of quinones as anolyte material in AORFB. Indeed, quinones are one of the most extensively studied organic anolyte materials in strong acidic^[23,32] or alkaline electrolytes.^[33] However, the performances of the state-of-the-art molecules still requires further improvements for AORFBs to become competitive against more mature technologies. Thus, much efforts are being devoted to searching for other candidates, or improve known compounds using molecular engineering.^[34] Specifically, one of the most used quinone derivatives in alkaline media is 2,6-dihydroxyanthraquinone (DHAQ).^[31] Hence, this molecule has been selected to probe the two main mechanisms of capacity fading in AORFB with the static cell, namely Faradaic imbalance caused by the inevitable entry of oxygen^[21] and the intrinsic stability of this molecule, benchmarking the results obtained with those reported in literature.

2.2.1 Probing oxygen leakage rate into the static cell.

As indicated above, a very relevant case study has been selected to illustrate the potential of the static cell to study sources of capacity fading in AORFBs. In particular, we focus first on Faradaic imbalance, which is one of the main pathways for capacity fading. Faradaic imbalance occurs when there is an uneven charge distribution between catholyte and anolyte due to the occurrence of parasitic side reactions. These reactions consume charge irreversibly, which can be remarkable under operation conditions, such as the oxygen reaction with reduced active species in the anolyte.^[21] Figure S7 schematically illustrates the concept of battery imbalance during the initial charge/discharge cycle in a balanced flow battery, attributed to oxygen-induced parasitic reactions occurring at the negative electrode. In view of its impact, it is crucial to determine the amount of oxygen entering the cell, as oxygen can lead not only to Faradaic imbalance but also to degradation of active species by different mechanisms. Thus, an experiment was designed to observe directly oxygen entry into the static battery. Specifically, an alkaline DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ RFB with an oversized anolyte containing 20% excess of DHAQ (assuming 1.75 exchanged electrons per DHAQ molecule) was used. This protocol ensures that the capacity fading is due to oxygen entering in the system. Note that battery and solutions were previously deoxygenated before injection, following the protocol outlined in Section S3 (Figure S8). When the oxygen-induced parasitic

reaction is the primary source of Faradaic imbalance and the battery is limited by the catholyte, it allows direct measurement of oxygen entry. Figure S9 illustrates schematically the observed imbalance in this case. In our scenario, part of the charge (e.g, 10 moles) is irreversibly consumed by the parasitic reaction in the anolyte (DHAQ) while the catholyte can achieve full charge in the first cycle. During the discharge process, the discharge capacity will be limited by the state of charge achieved in the anolyte, hence the catholyte will remain partially charged at the end of the discharge (10 moles). Thus, the storage capacity of the battery decreases in the second cycle because only 90 moles out of 100 of catholyte are available to be charged since no excess of ferrocyanide was initially added. When an oversized catholyte is used, the excess of ferrocyanide enables the battery to be fully charged in the second cycle. Note that Faradaic imbalance will occur from the first cycle in both a balanced-battery and an oversized-anolyte battery. However, it is not simple to assemble a balanced-battery since small errors in measuring the volumes and properly drying the organic compounds can lead to a slightly unbalanced-battery, in which case the limiting side will be unknown. Thus, using oversized-anolyte battery is a more reliable option.

Figure 5. Determination of oxygen entry rate in a flow/static battery by oversizing the anolyte. (A) Discharge capacity and Coulombic efficiency of a DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ flow battery versus cycling time at $\pm 30 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. Catholyte: 13 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide in 1M KCl; anolyte: 13 mL of 0.2 M DHAQ in 1.4 M KOH. (B) Comparison of discharge capacity versus time for a static battery cycled outside an Ar-filled box (blue) and one cycled inside an Ar-filled box (green) at $\pm 5 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. Catholyte: approx. 0.37 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide in 1M KOH; anolyte: approx. 0.37 mL of 0.2 M DHAQ in 1.4 M KOH with a pH of 14.

In the case of a flow battery with oversized anolyte cycled under Argon overpressure, a capacity fading rate of $11.04\% \text{ day}^{-1}$ over 3.7 days was noted (Figure 5A) due to oxygen-induced Faraday imbalance. The capacity fading of a flow battery operated without Argon overpressure (Figure S10) increased up to $13.2\% \text{ day}^{-1}$ over 3.7 days, illustrating the problem of oxygen influx in flowing conditions. In turn, the evolution of discharge capacity versus time of static batteries cycled inside (blue) and outside an Ar-filled box (green) is compared in Figure 5B. Note that in both cases the electrolyte was injected in the static cells after deoxygenation. A singular feature that can only be seen in alkaline static batteries with oversized anolyte is an initial capacity increase due to an activation process, since this bump disappears when the injected cell is left at OCV for 45 hours, as can be seen in Figure S11. Interestingly, cycling the static battery in air results in a capacity loss of $3.36\% \text{ day}^{-1}$ calculated over 30 cycling days (Figure 5B, blue), which indicates that the oxygen entry rate in the static battery is slower (3.3-fold) than in the flow battery. This is considerably advantageous in terms of cost saving and resource needs, such as peristaltic pumps and argon line.

However, for conducting tests in total absence of oxygen, the static cell was introduced in an argon-filled box that we developed (abbreviated as Ar-box). The system consists of a simple lunch box with holes to fit connecting cables to the static battery and a lid pierced by a needle for the Argon inlet (Figure S12). Cycling the cell inside this Ar-box, it was possible to prevent oxygen entry, obtaining a capacity fading rate of $0.091\% \text{ day}^{-1}$ from day 5 to 17 (Figure 5B, green). This set-up allows evaluating active species under glovebox conditions in a cost-effective and straightforward way in laboratories where expensive gloveboxes that contains purification are not available. The increase in discharge capacity loss, up to $1.04\% \text{ day}^{-1}$, noted after 20 days (Figure 5B, green) is due to dimerization of a product of disproportionation of charged DHAQ,^[31] as it is apparent from the charge and discharge profiles (Figure S13, A). Note that dimer formation is more clearly visible in the derivative signal (Figure S13, B). It is possible to observe this capacity loss after 20 days because the excess of DHAQ at the anolyte has been most likely consumed by this time, allowing DHAQ degradation to be seen. The reduced DHAQ (DHAHQ^{4-}) undergoes disproportionation to DHAQ and 2,6-dihydroxyanthrone (DHA^{3-}), as depicted in Figure S14. In these alkaline conditions, DHA^{3-} is easily oxidized through a one-electron, followed by an irreversible radical dimerization $(\text{DHA})_2^{4-}$. The degradation rate depends on concentration and depth of

charge^[31]. The values (1.04 % day⁻¹) obtained in our simple Ar-box in the second stage (excess of DHAQ is consumed) are in between the capacity fading values reported when using a glovebox, which varies from 4.6 % day⁻¹ for fully charged DHAQ anolyte^[35] to 0.14 % day⁻¹ when charged to 88 % depth of charge for 0.1 M DHAQ.^[31] It should be noted that dimer formation is not seen in charge and discharge profiles for the static battery cycled outside the Ar-box (Figure S15), as opposed to the battery cycled inside the Ar-box (Figure S13). This can be attributed to the leakage of small amounts of oxygen favoring the oxidation of DHA³⁻ to DHAQ over dimerization (Figure S14), particularly at low DHA³⁻ concentrations, as in our case with an oversized anolyte (DHAQ).

2.2.2 Probing capacity fading of an alkaline DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ RFB due to dimerization.

In this section, different conditions were selected to operate the alkaline DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ battery with the aim of further demonstrating that the static cell can be a useful tool to explore electrolyte degradation mechanisms. As explained in previous section, DHAQ was chosen as stability case study since its degradation mechanism has been extensively studied in literature. Stability of DHAQ will be evaluated in the static cell both inside and outside the homemade Ar-box. In this specific case of assessing anolyte stability, the catholyte was oversized to prevent capacity fading due to Faradaic imbalance caused by several parasitic reactions at the anolyte such as the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) or the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). In this configuration, capacity will be limited by the anolyte. Catholyte was oversized by introducing an excess of potassium ferrocyanide in a static cell assembled with two Viton® gaskets and two carbon felts in the catholyte compartment (Figure S16). As pointed out in Section 3.2.1, the stability of a redox molecule is affected by its state of charge (S.O.C), hence it is important to determine the utilization rate of the electrolyte for stability assessment. A CCCV evaluation protocol was established, enabling 100% utilization rate of DHAQ, as shown in Table S14.

Figure 6A compares DHAQ stability in a DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ static battery cycled inside and outside the Ar-box charged at full S.O.C. Interestingly, capacity fading rate over 22 days is lower outside the Ar-box, 1.30 % day⁻¹, than inside the Ar-box, amounting to 2.55 % day⁻¹. The slower capacity fading outside the Ar-box can be attributed to a small amount of oxygen entering the cell that favors oxidation of DHA³⁻ to DHAQ over dimerization (Figure S14).^[31] Indeed, the derivative capacity profile clearly reveals dimer formation inside the Ar-box

(Figure S17, region 0.6-0.9 V), whereas no dimers were observed outside the Ar-box after 10 cycling days. Static battery results are in agreement with previous reports by Aziz's group that controlled oxygen ingress could prevent capacity fading due to dimerization.^[31] Thus, the static cell allows exploring stability and degradation mechanism of AORFB electrolyte species using considerably smaller amounts of material.

Figure 6. Comparison of discharge capacity versus time (days) for a DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ static battery cycled outside (blue) and inside Ar-box (green) at $\pm 5 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ with voltage limits of +1.6 / +0.5 V. Catholyte: approx. 0.96 mL of 0.3 M potassium ferrocyanide in 1M KOH; anolyte: approx. 0.48 mL of 0.2 M DHAQ in 1.4 M KOH with a pH of 14.

2.3. Probing degradation mechanism of Viologen//K₄Fe(CN)₆ neutral RFB with the static cell.

The viologen family was selected as a second case study to illustrate the capability of the developed static cell for testing stability of electrolyte active molecules in different pH media. Viologen derivatives are the most commonly used active species for neutral pH anolyte due to their low cost, tunability, high solubility and fast electrochemistry kinetics.^[36] In particular,

1,1-bis[3-sulfonatopropyl]-4,4-bipyridinium (BSPrV) is one of the most reported viologen derivative for AORFB anolyte in the literature, in view of its high cyclability.^[37] Therefore, the stability of BSPrV in neutral media has been explored with the methodology developed. So far, the best cyclability performance has been achieved inside a glovebox to prevent the impact of oxygen traces in the anolyte in this molecule.^[37–39] Oxygen-free conditions are crucial because oxygen reduction consumes charge irreversible during the charging process, causing Faradaic Imbalance, but also generates hydroxide anions that accelerate viologen degradation. Among the degradation mechanisms proposed in literature, viologen dealkylation via nucleophilic attack of hydroxide anions, resulting in cleavage of C(alkyl)-N bond, has been proposed by several groups when operating outside an Ar-filled glovebox.^[40–42] More recently, the mechanism was demonstrated by our group, revealing an increase of the electrolyte pH value caused by hydroxide anions generated by oxygen reduction ($\text{O}_2 + 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + 4 \text{e}^- \rightarrow 4 \text{OH}^-$), which are responsible for viologen dealkylation.^[2]

In this context, the cycling stability of the viologen derivative BSPrV was evaluated in a static cell inside and outside the Ar-box using an oversized potassium ferrocyanide catholyte so that anolyte becomes the capacity-limiting side. Discharge capacity retention under both (aerobic and anaerobic) conditions is compared in Figure 7. The most remarkable difference arises after 11 cycling days (Figure 7, area shaded in red), when discharge capacity of the battery operated outside the Ar-box starts declining rapidly at a capacity fading rate of 4.08 \% day^{-1} during the last 100 hours (day 14–18) of the experiment. This value is similar to the one noted for the DHAQ// $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ static battery also operated outside the Ar-box (Section 3.2.1), where capacity fading rate due to oxygen leaking in the static cell was 3.36 \% day^{-1} . As in that case, this capacity fade would indicate consumption of the excess ferrocyanide buffer added to mitigate the impact of Faradaic imbalance caused by the inevitable oxygen ingress in the cell. On the contrary, capacity of the battery cycled inside the Ar-box remains stable also after the first 11 days, with a total capacity fading rate over 20 days of 0.44 \% day^{-1} , a value fully consistent with those reported in literature.^[37–39,43] Capacity fading of both batteries in the initial 10 days (before the excess of ferrocyanide in the cell outside the Ar-box is consumed), is comparable at 0.7 \% day^{-1} . Overall, these values are much better than those obtained in a flow battery with an oversized catholyte under argon overpressure, where capacity fading rate over 3 days was $10.32 \text{ \% day}^{-1}$.^[2] The increased fading rate points at a higher oxygen entry in the flow battery, and a consequent higher generation of hydroxide anions that raises the anolyte pH. These hydroxyl ions are involved in viologen dealkylation, which is the primary

degradation mechanism responsible for the rapid capacity fading observed in the initial cycles without Ar-filled glovebox for viologen-based neutral analytes.

Figure 7. Capacity retention versus time for a BSPrV//K₄Fe(CN)₆ static battery cycled outside (blue) and inside an Ar-box (green) at $\pm 5 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ with voltage limits of 1.1 V / +0.5 V. Catholyte: approx. 0.6 mL of 0.3 M potassium ferrocyanide in 1M KCl with a pH of 7.1; anolyte: approx. 0.6 mL of 0.2 M BSPrV in 1 M KCl with a pH of 3.8.

Stability, among other key properties of electroactive species can be tuned by molecular engineering. This strategy has been applied to enhance stability of viologen derivatives, making them more resistant to alkaline conditions induced by oxygen reduction. Specifically, our group recently proposed a viologen derivative, 1,1'-bis(1-methyl-3-sulfonatopropyl)-4,4'-bipyridinium (BS3BuV) molecular engineered to become more resistant to dealkylation in alkaline media.^[2] Due to its higher stability, this derivative was selected for a comparative study with the BSPrV performed with static cells where the catholyte compartment was also oversized. Capacity retention of static batteries with each viologen derivative cycled inside the Ar-box is compared in Figure 8. Both derivatives exhibit a capacity fading rate of 0.44 \% day^{-1} over the course of 20 days, a value comparable with those reported in flow systems.^[37–39,43] However, despite reaching similar capacity retention after 20 days, capacity decay of BSPrV anolyte is initially much faster than that of the modified viologen (BS3BuV). For the former, the initial steep decay is smoothed after approximately 4 days (Figure 8, green arrow) while for the latter smoothing takes around 11 days (Figure 8, red arrow). During this time,

capacity fading is mostly dominated by viologen degradation due to dealkylation by nucleophilic attack of hydroxyl anions produced by reduction of oxygen traces inside the cell. In the later stage, the prevailing mechanism is viologen degradation through dimerization (Figure S18), a mechanism occurring in absence of oxygen. During this period, capacity fading of both viologen derivatives is $0.2\% \text{ day}^{-1}$ over the last 14 days. The occurrence of the second stage indicates that dealkylation of viologen consumes hydroxy anions at higher rate than oxygen is entering the cell. The longer first stage of BS3BuV reveals a higher stability against dealkylation, which is consistent with our previous work using flowing conditions. Furthermore, Figure 8 also shows that the excess of ferrocyanide is not consumed for at least 25 days. Applying Faraday's law, it is estimated an oxygen influx rate below 450 nanomoles per day, equivalent to the consumption of a maximum of 1.2 mAh of excess charge within 25 days. These findings suggest that expensive Ar-filled gloveboxes with purification systems may not be essential for conducting preliminary medium-term measurements, such as those spanning 25 days, democratizing access to high-performance battery research.

Figure 8. Evolution of capacity retention versus time for static batteries with 2 different viologen anolytes, BSPrV (green) and BS3BuV (red) and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ catholyte, cycled inside an Ar-box at $\pm 5 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ with voltage limits of 1.1 V / +0.5 V. Catholyte: approx. 0.6 mL of 0.3 M potassium ferrocyanide in 1M KCl with a pH of 7.1; anolyte: approx. 0.6 mL of 0.2 M BSPrV or BS3BuV in 1 M KCl with a pH of 3.8.

3. Conclusions

Identifying the processes that cause energy storage capacity fading in AORFB is crucial for deployment of this promising technology, as it allows designing strategies to prevent or mitigate this limitation. This requires applying several techniques as screening filters, mostly when novel active species for the electrolytes are sought and their performance interrogated. In this work, we demonstrate the power of miniaturized static cells as a screening tool for new active species candidates for AORFB as well as for exploring their degradation mechanism. Compared to conventional assessment in flow systems, the proposed static cell methodology requires smaller amount of active material (in the milligram rather than the gram scale), reducing considerably synthetic efforts, material consumption and accessible to any research laboratory. The detailed configuration and assembly of the static battery cell designed, 3D-printed and validated using potassium ferrocyanide as model system is presented. Additionally, an experimental set-up to prevent oxygen entry into the cell is reported. The methodology has been successfully applied to explore the origin of capacity fading of different AORFB chemistries in alkaline and neutral media. In anthraquinone-based alkaline anolyte, the static cell allowed us to evaluate capacity fading due to oxygen entry and determine the amount of oxygen entering the battery, which was lower than in flow systems. Moreover, cycling conditions to minimize anthraquinone degradation by dimerization were identified, namely avoiding charge to 100% of S.O.C and allowing entry of a small amount of oxygen. In viologen-based neutral anolyte, the impact of oxygen on the battery capacity retention was assessed using two viologen derivatives and both aerobic/anaerobic conditions. It was possible to observe different capacity fading sources, from Faradaic imbalance due to parasitic side reactions to viologen degradation by different mechanisms, dealkylation of discharged and dimerization of charged viologen. In summary, we believe that this methodology can contribute to a faster large-scale deployment of AORFB by identifying high-performing active molecules while providing better understanding of degradation processes that limit their cycling stability.

4. Experimental section

4.1. Materials

Potassium ferrocyanide (II) trihydrate, potassium ferricyanide (III) (> 98%, Thermoscientific), fluorescein and KOH (VWR) were used as received. The synthetic procedure for the preparation of 2,6-dihydroxanthraquinone (DHAQ), 1,1'-bis[3-sulfonatopropyl]-4,4'-bipyridinium (BSP₃V) and 1,1'-bis(1-methyl-3-sulfonatopropyl)-4,4'-bipyridinium (BS₃BuV) were previously reported (Section S1).

4.2. Preparation of electrolytes.

In the fluorescein//K₄Fe(CN)₆ flow battery, the catholyte was prepared by dissolving potassium ferrocyanide in 1 M KOH to afford 45 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide electrolyte. The anolyte was prepared by dissolving fluoresceine in 1.4 M KOH to afford 10 mL of 0.2 M fluoresceine electrolyte and it was purged with argon prior to use. All electrolytes were prepared with deionized water.

In the DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ flow battery, the catholyte was prepared by dissolving potassium ferrocyanide in 1 M KOH to afford 13 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide electrolyte. The anolyte was prepared by dissolving DHAQ in 1.4 M KOH to afford 13 mL of 0.2 M DHAQ electrolyte and it was purged with argon prior to use. All electrolytes were prepared with deionized water.

In the symmetric K₃Fe(CN)₆//K₄Fe(CN)₆ static cell, the catholyte was prepared by dissolving potassium ferrocyanide in 0.5 M KCl to afford 2 mL of 0.1 M ferrocyanide electrolyte. The anolyte was prepared by dissolving potassium ferricyanide to afford 2 mL of 0.6 M ferricyanide (oversized counter-compartment).

In the DHAQ//K₄Fe(CN)₆ static battery, the catholyte was prepared by dissolving potassium ferrocyanide in 1 M KOH to afford 2 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide electrolyte. In the case of this type of cell with oversized catholyte, 2 mL of this solution was prepared. The anolyte was prepared by dissolving DHAQ in 1.4 M KOH to afford 2 mL of 0.2 M DHAQ electrolyte. All electrolytes were prepared with deionized water and both were purged with argon prior to use.

In the fluorescein//K₄Fe(CN)₆ static battery, the catholyte was prepared by dissolving potassium ferrocyanide in 1 M KOH to afford 2 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide electrolyte. The anolyte was prepared by dissolving fluorescein in 1.4 M KOH to afford 2 mL of 0.2 M fluoresceine electrolyte and it was purged with argon prior to use. All electrolytes were prepared with deionized water.

In the viologen//K₄Fe(CN)₆ static battery, the catholyte was prepared by dissolving potassium ferrocyanide in 1 M KCl to afford 2 mL of 0.3 M ferrocyanide electrolyte. The anolyte was prepared by dissolving the viologen derivative in 1 M KCl to afford 2 mL of 0.2 M viologen electrolyte. All electrolytes were prepared with deionized water and both were purged with argon prior to use.

4.3. Battery setup

Flow battery. A filter-pressed flow cell using expanded graphite (SGL Carbon), graphite felt (SGL Carbon) and Nafion 212 (Ion Power) as current collector, electrode and ion selective membrane, respectively was used. The projected area of the cell was 10 cm². A peristaltic pump (MasterFlex L/S) was used to provide a flow rate of 50 mL·min⁻¹.

Static batteries. The static cell (Figure 3) was designed using the SketchUp software and manufactured using an Ultraviolet (UV) Liquid Cristal Display (LCD) - based stereolithography (SLA) 3D printer (Photon Mono SE, Anycubic) and a commercial clear resin (Anycubic). After the cleaning procedure (with 70% isopropanol solution), the printed pieces were assembled (section 3.1, Figure 3). A filter-pressed static cell using expanded graphite (SGL Carbon), graphite felt (SGL Carbon) and Nafion 212 (Ion Power) as current collector, electrode and ion selective membrane, respectively was used. The projected area of the cell was 3 cm².

4.4. Electrochemical characterization

Cyclic voltammetry was carried out using an Autolab PGSTAT12 (Methrom-Autolab, The Netherlands) controlled by NOVA 2.1.3 software. The experimental setup consisted of a three-electrode cell with a polished glassy carbon working electrode (area = 7 mm²), a Pt wire counter electrode (99% purity) and a Hg/HgO (1 M NaOH) reference electrode. For battery testing, galvanostatic and potentiostatic charge-discharge measurements were performed using a Neware BTS battery testing system CT-40087-5V6A-S1.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge financial support by the Spanish Government Agencia Estatal de Investigación/Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, Grants PID2021-124974OB-C22, PID2023-148198NB-C21, CNS2023-145051 and Ramon y Cajal award (RYC2018-026086-I), as well as the MeBattery project. MeBattery has received funding from the European Innovation Council of the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101046742. This work was also supported by the Regional Government of Castilla y Leon (Junta de Castilla y Leon) and by the Ministry of Science and Innovation MICIN and the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR (C17. I1).

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Revised: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Published online: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

References

- [1] M. Zhang, T. Li, X. Liu, C. Zhang, X. Li, *Adv Funct Mater* **2024**, *34*, 2312608.
- [2] R. Rubio-Presa, L. Lubián, M. Borlaf, E. Ventosa, R. Sanz, *ACS Mater Lett* **2023**, *5*, 798.
- [3] E. Sánchez-Díez, E. Ventosa, M. Guarnieri, A. Trovò, C. Flox, R. Marcilla, F. Soavi, P. Mazur, E. Aranzabe, R. Ferret, *J Power Sources* **2021**, *481*, 228804.
- [4] P. Leung, A. A. Shah, L. Sanz, C. Flox, J. R. Morante, Q. Xu, M. R. Mohamed, C. Ponce de León, F. C. Walsh, *J Power Sources* **2017**, *360*, 243.
- [5] H. Sun, F. Hu, Z. Jiang, Z. Cui, M. Ravivarma, H. Fan, J. Song, D. Kong, *Chem Synth* **2023**, *3*, 33.
- [6] J. Chai, A. Lashgari, J. Jiang in *Clean Energy Materials*, Vol. 1364, (Eds: L. Quin and L.S. Fan), American Chemical Society, **2020**, Chapter 1, pp. 1–47.
- [7] S. de la Parra, J. A. Tamayo-Ramos, R. Rubio-Presa, D. Perez-Antolin, V. Ruiz, R. Sanz, C. Rumbo, E. Ventosa, *ChemSusChem* **2023**, *16*, e202300626.
- [8] C. Wang, Z. Yang, Y. Wang, P. Zhao, W. Yan, G. Zhu, L. Ma, B. Yu, L. Wang, G. Li, J. Liu, Z. Jin, *ACS Energy Lett* **2018**, *3*, 2404.
- [9] Y. Ji, M. A. Goulet, D. A. Pollack, D. G. Kwabi, S. Jin, D. De Porcellinis, E. F. Kerr, R. G. Gordon, M. J. Aziz, *Adv Energy Mater* **2019**, *9*, 1900039.
- [10] K. Lin, Q. Chen, M. R. Gerhardt, L. Tong, S. B. Kim, L. Eisenach, A. W. Valle, D. Hardee, R. G. Gordon, M. J. Aziz, M. P. Marshak, *Science* **2015**, *349*, 1529.
- [11] Y. Cho, H. Kye, B.-G. Kim, J. E. Kwon, *J Ind Eng Chem* **2024**, *136*, 73.
- [12] T. Yin, J. Duanmu, L. Liu, *J Mater Chem A* **2024**, *12*, 15519.
- [13] M. E. Carrington, K. Sokołowski, E. Jónsson, E. W. Zhao, A. M. Graf, I. Temprano, J. A. McCune, C. P. Grey, O. A. Scherman, *Nature* **2023**, *623*, 949.
- [14] K. Peng, G. Tang, C. Zhang, X. Yang, P. Zuo, Z. Xiang, Z. Yao, Z. Yang, T. Xu, *J. Energy Chem.* **2024**, *96*, 89.
- [15] A. Hollas, X. Wei, V. Murugesan, Z. Nie, B. Li, D. Reed, J. Liu, V. Sprenkle, W. Wang, *Nat Energy* **2018**, *3*, 508.
- [16] T. Páez, A. Martínez-Cuezva, J. Palma, E. Ventosa, *J Power Sources* **2020**, *471*, 228453.
- [17] B. Hu, C. Debruler, Z. Rhodes, T. L. Liu, *J Am Chem Soc* **2017**, *139*, 1207.
- [18] Y. Liu, Q. Chen, X. Zhang, J. Ran, X. Han, Z. Yang, T. Xu, *Curr Opin Electrochem* **2022**, *32*, 100895.
- [19] K. Wedege, E. Dražević, D. Konya, A. Bientien, *Sci Rep* **2016**, *6*, 39101.
- [20] E. J. Latchem, T. Kress, P. A. A. Klusener, R. V. Kumar, C. Forse, *J Phys Chem Lett* **2024**, *15*, 1.
- [21] T. Páez, A. Martínez-Cuezva, R. Marcilla, J. Palma, E. Ventosa, *J Power Sources* **2021**, *512*, 230516.
- [22] C. De La Cruz, A. Molina, N. Patil, E. Ventosa, R. Marcilla, A. Mavrandonakis, *Sustain Energy Fuels* **2020**, *4*, 5513.
- [23] D. P. Tabor, R. Gómez-Bombarelli, L. Tong, R. G. Gordon, M. J. Aziz, A. Aspuru-Guzik, *J Mater Chem A* **2019**, *7*, 12833.
- [24] X. Qian, D. R. Chang, S. Jung, *J. Chem. Eng* **2022**, *429*, 132136.

- [25] L. C. Yu, Y. C. Luo, W. Feng, S. Zhang, X. Zhang, *J Mater Chem* **2023**, *11*, 18911.
- [26] M. J. Baran, M. N. Braten, E. C. Montoto, Z. T. Gossage, L. Ma, E. Chénard, J. S. Moore, J. Rodríguez-López, B. A. Helms, *Chem. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 3861.
- [27] S. Zhang, X. Li, D. Chu, *Electrochim Acta* **2016**, *190*, 737.
- [28] H. Li, H. Fan, B. Hu, L. Hu, G. Chang, J. Song, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, *60*, 26971.
- [29] W. Xiang, M. Yang, M. Ding, X. Chen, J. Liu, G. Zhou, C. Jia, G. I. N. Waterhouse, *Energy Storage Mater* **2023**, *61*, 102894.
- [30] M.-A. Goulet, M. J. Aziz, *J Electrochem Soc* **2018**, *165*, A1466.
- [31] M. A. Goulet, L. Tong, D. A. Pollack, D. P. Tabor, S. A. Odom, A. Aspuru-Guzik, E. E. Kwan, R. G. Gordon, M. J. Aziz, *J Am Chem Soc* **2020**, *141*, 8014.
- [32] M. R. Gerhardt, L. Tong, R. Gómez-Bombarelli, Q. Chen, M. P. Marshak, C. J. Galvin, A. Aspuru-Guzik, R. G. Gordon, M. J. Aziz, *Adv Energy Mater* **2017**, *7*, 1601488.
- [33] B. Lu, K. Yu, W. Shao, Y. Ji, F. Zhang, *Curr Opin Green Sustain Chem* **2024**, *47*, 100905.
- [34] Y. Jing, E. M. Fell, M. Wu, S. Jin, Y. Ji, D. A. Pollack, Z. Tang, D. Ding, M. Bahari, M. A. Goulet, T. Tsukamoto, R. G. Gordon, M. J. Aziz, *ACS Energy Lett* **2022**, *7*, 226.
- [35] E. M. Fell, M. J. Aziz, *J Electrochem Soc* **2023**, *170*, 100507.
- [36] E. Sánchez-Díez, E. Ventosa, M. Guarnieri, A. Trovò, C. Flox, R. Marcilla, F. Soavi, P. Mazur, E. Aranzabe, R. Ferret, *J Power Sources* **2021**, *481*, 228804.
- [37] J. Luo, B. Hu, C. Debruler, Y. Bi, Y. Zhao, B. Yuan, M. Hu, W. Wu, T. L. Liu, *Joule* **2019**, *3*, 149.
- [38] C. Debruler, B. Hu, J. Moss, J. Luo, T. L. Liu, *ACS Energy Lett* **2018**, *3*, 663.
- [39] D. G. Kwabi, Y. Ji, M. J. Aziz, *Chem Rev* **2020**, *120*, 6467.
- [40] C. L. Bird, A. T. Kuhn, *Chem Soc Rev* **1981**, *10*, 49.
- [41] A. L. Rieger, J. O. Edwards, *J Org Chem* **1988**, *53*, 1481.
- [42] E. S. Beh, D. De Porcellinis, R. L. Gracia, K. T. Xia, R. G. Gordon, M. J. Aziz, *ACS Energy Lett* **2017**, *2*, 639.
- [43] Q. Chen, Y. Lv, Z. Yuan, X. Li, G. Yu, Z. Yang, T. Xu, *Adv Funct Mater* **2022**, *32*, 2108777.

The static cell is power tool in the search for the ultimate organic molecules bridging the gap between fundamental electrochemical characterization and full redox flow battery. The absence of flowing condition simplifies the system facilitating a low-cost and low-effort investigation of degradation mechanism.

Lara Lubian^[a,b], Ruben Rubio-Presa^[a], Roberto Sanz,^[b] Virginia Ruiz^[a,b], Edgar Ventosa**

On the Relevance of Static Cells for Fast Scale-Up of New Redox Flow Battery Chemistries

